

Appendix A. Respondent Demographic Characteristics

Table. Respondent characteristics (N = 406)

Variable	Category	n	%
Age	≤25–30	11	27.
	years	0	1
	30–45	14	34.
	years	1	7
	46–60	89	21.
	years		9
	>60 years	66	16.
			3
Employment status	Permanent	31	76.
		0	4
	Contract	96	23.
			6
Years of service	0–5 years	18	46.
		8	3
	6–10	18	44.
	years	1	6
	11–20	37	9.1
	years		
Highest education	Bachelor's degree	7	1.7
	Master's degree	35	87.
		7	9
	Doctoral degree	42	10.
			3
Academic rank	Assistant Professor	19	47.
		2	3
	Lecturer	16	40.
		5	6
	Associate Professor	36	8.9
	Professor	13	3.2
Marital status	Single	39	9.6
	Married	36	88.
		0	7
	Previously married	7	1.7

Appendix B. Research Questionnaire

Table Questionnaire Scales and Items for the Research Model Construct

Code	Variable and Measurement Items	Type
X1	WORK-LIFE BALANCE (WLB)	
X1.1	I can comfortably adjust my teaching schedules and academic reporting to manage my personal and family commitments.	Positive
X1.2	The institutional policies allow me to fulfill Tri Dharma assignments without being strictly bound to conventional campus working hours.	Positive
X1.3	I am able to freely allocate optimal time for student consultations and research tasks without disrupting my personal life.	Positive
X1.4	I can effectively schedule my administrative duties (e.g., BKD reporting) so that they do not interfere with important personal activities.	Positive
X2	WORKLOAD (BEBAN KERJA)	
X2.1	The distribution of academic responsibilities and administrative workloads among faculty members in my department is fair and well-proportioned.	Positive
X2.2	My total assigned tasks remain within my actual capacity to achieve optimal results without sacrificing my health or quality of life.	Positive
X2.3	<i>The volume of academic and administrative tasks frequently exceeds my available time, energy, and physical capacity.</i>	Reverse (*)
X2.4	<i>Managing multiple academic deadlines simultaneously often subjects me to severe emotional or physical stress.</i>	Reverse (*)
X3	JOB STRESS (STRES KERJA)	
X3.1	The university actively provides structural facilities that support mental well-being, such as family-friendly policies and clear leave procedures.	Positive
X3.2	My administrative obstacles and structural assignments can be addressed efficiently without creating overwhelming work pressures.	Positive
X3.3	The university formalizes actionable mental and physical health policies (e.g., counseling access, stress management programs) to foster a healthy workplace.	Positive
X3.4	The welfare programs provided by the institution are strategically designed to improve the holistic quality of life for faculty members.	Positive

Table S3. Questionnaire Scales and Items for the Research Model Construct

Code	Variable and Measurement Items	Type
M	PROTEAN CAREER ORIENTATION (PCO)	
M1.1	I actively design my career development to align with my personal values and goals.	Positive
M1.2	I make career decisions based on my own understanding of my life priorities and direction.	Positive
M1.3	I regularly update my professional competencies (e.g., research methods, digital teaching tools, academic publishing) to navigate institutional changes.	Positive
M1.4	I independently manage my academic career path rather than relying on institutional directives or external triggers.	Positive
Z	SUPPORTIVE ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE (SOC)	
Z1.1	The management openly and transparently communicates important policies and institutional structural decisions.	Positive
Z1.2	Leadership provides adequate space for faculty members to participate in academic decision-making processes.	Positive
Z1.3	The institution provides concrete administrative and financial support for professional development and research.	Positive
Z1.4	My institution offers actionable policies that accommodate work-life balance and family responsibilities.	Positive
Z1.5	The administrative workload distributed by the institution remains within a reasonable capacity that does not jeopardize personal well-being.	Positive
Y	JOB SATISFACTION	
Y1.1	I am satisfied with my current salary as it fairly reflects my professional contribution to the institution.	Positive
Y1.2	The academic promotion criteria are transparent, clearly written, and strictly merit-based.	Positive
Y1.3	My superiors provide constructive, clear, and supportive supervision regarding my academic duties.	Positive
Y1.4	The institutional benefits framework (e.g., health insurance, research incentives) adequately covers my professional needs.	Positive
Y1.5	Contingent rewards and formal appreciation are granted fairly based on actual performance rather than personal proximity.	Positive
Y1.6	Operating procedures and administrative rules are streamlined, efficient, and free from burdensome bureaucracy.	Positive
Y1.7	My coworkers are collaborative, supportive, and professional when resolving academic tasks.	Positive
Y1.8	The nature of my academic work provides personal satisfaction and valuable opportunities for intellectual growth.	Positive
Y1.9	Internal organizational communication across different units supports the smooth execution of my responsibilities.	Positive